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Place of Emotions In Marketing And Its Importance In ELM Model

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Abstract

Until recently, emotions were not one of the most precious elements of marketing. There are theoretical and empirical models that show that emotions affect perception, decision, motivation, and consumer behaviour of the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM). ELM can be defined as a model of processing probability; this theory assumes that it will continue to do with its reflections on consumers in various directions. The Elaboration Likelihood Model explains how persuasion messages work in changing the attitude of the reader or consumers. It is very crucial for corporations and advertisement agencies, to design their marketing strategies and understand the attitudes of people. Out of all attitudes, the paper will analyse how emotions can impact on marketing.

Keywords: Emotions, Marketing, ELM Model, Consumer Behavior, Sensory Marketing

1. Introduction

Over the past twenty years, the nature of marketing as a field of study, research, and business philosophy has seen significant changes. These are reflected in new marketing concepts emphasizing aspects of service, perception, partnership, corporate social responsibility, and branding. Current researches are focusing on marketing based on human emotions. Hence, development of a new marketing logic is created where the focus of the offer is shifting from goods to the transaction. The service aspect is focusing on intangible components, predominant regarding customer perception and decision-making processes. The paper aims to point out the importance of emotions in contemporary marketing and its importance in the ELM model.

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1.1 Place of emotions in marketing

Taking into account the emotions as a critical element of consumer behavior is increasingly occupied by practitioners as well as consumer behavior theorists. Emotions can be defined as a complex psychological phenomenon, including personal survival, neurophysiological processes, and manifestations such as facial expression, behavior, verbal response (Boguszewicz-Kreft, 2009, p. 15-20). Investigating consumer emotions is all the more critical for marketing researchers because it represents a mechanism that has significant consumer interest. Therefore, the value of the offer is no longer based only on physical characteristics, but also on purchasing experience and consumer consumption. When the consumer purchases or consumes a product or service continuously, an intense emotion concerning a product and the environment is developed. A consumer without emotional expression would be tough to identify when it comes to creating a business offer. Therefore, from the marketing manager perspective, emotion can be regarded as an aid to know the consumer.

Business-based marketing is a set of methods that serves to support positive attitudes and consumer behavior so that it can achieve its market goals. It means that the role of marketing in terms of business goals is to achieve compliance with its emotional expressions. Consequently, the explanation of consumer emotions will have to be considered as a specific area of marketing in the future and to integrate them among activities that aim to influence attitudes and consumer behavior. Figure 1 characterizes this role of marketing in terms of emotions.

Figure 1. Integrating Emotions into the Business

The consumer's decision (purchase order) is made based on personal experience in which consumer assesses the characteristics, functions of the products and compares them to each other in order to make a final decision on the product-need-relationship. Consequently, human decisions are primarily based on impression and experience. In this context, a marketing manager must be able to manage this behavior by influencing the human senses. Therefore, it also seems increasingly important to pay attention to the issue of sensory marketing, which can evaluate and exploit the influence of the senses in perceiving the product to consumers at the stage of comparison, selection, use and evaluation of the purchase for the benefit of the enterprise. It also becomes the basis for a strategy for differentiating businesses based on the personal value of a product that is perceived by consumers.

2. ELM Models

Traditional marketing based on the company's ability to provide products that meet the needs of consumer segments. This type of marketing based on segmentation that takes into account consumer rationality. The consumer perceived as an individual who thinks logically, based on reasoning, and deciding on problems in order to achieve a solution. On the contrary, current models emphasize that emotions have an impact on consumer acceptance, which is not always rational, even if it is considered to be the most optimal. Consequently, the cognitive decision-making process is not the only way for the consumer to gain a positive belief in the offer.

Currently, one of the most important and widely used models is the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), which is a probabilistic model that integrates two different considerations, these are cognitive and emotional, involving different human brain zones. These processes are creating the ultimate belief of the consumer, positive or negative emotions, and are often contradictory. This means that the cognitive process, which is more slowly enforced by the individual, is often dominated by an emotional process that is almost instant. On this theoretical basis, other models of consumer beliefs, such as dual MOA (motivation, opportunity, ability), LISA (logic, imitation, sentiment, automotive), were developed, based on the theory of limited irrationality and MAC (memory, impression, cognition) and the like.

The probability model was proposed by P. E. Petty and J. T. Caciopp in 1986 (Barnier, 2006). Its foundations is based on two theoretical paradigms. The first is the change in attitude, which was proposed by W. J. McGuire in 1969, and is interested in the process of information processing for individuals. The second concerns the theory of cognitive response developed by G. G. Greenwald in 1968. According to this author, the influence of persuasive messages depends on the nature of the cognitive response generated by an individual by comparing the information contained in, for example, an advertising message with his current attitude.

The model explains two basic consumer belief processes. The convenient way is the likelihood of creating an individual's beliefs, which means that the individual creates his / her attitude or beliefs based on his specific mechanisms of learning or by changing his mind in the process of engaging in business communication through messages, arguments, reports, and the like. The authors of the model define the likelihood of creating beliefs as a degree by which an individual generates product-related ideas based on the above main arguments in a communication message. IT happened when an individual critically evaluates the information being processed, which is vital for his or her change of attitude. The second is the so-called peripheral way that provides the recipient with additional, side signs to create a belief. These characters are based on emotions rather than logic, which makes it easier and faster to change attitudes (Darpy and Volle, 2007). These used when the message is challenging to process for the recipient, or if the message is challenging to process incomprehensible. Therefore, it seeks to find such understandable characters that relate, for example, to the source's credibility, to facilitate the process of evaluating the report. Consequently, by using a central and peripheral way of arguing in an advertising message, the consumer helps to better understand the message content without complicated cognitive processing of information.

The authors formulate seven basic principles on which their model tests. These are:

- The strategy used by the recipient to select the right argument, with limited information processing capability. It means that each is motivated to take their own and most correct attitude, allowing them to reduce their risk of product selection;
- Situational and individual variables were affecting the recipient's cognitive thinking. This situation is particular and varies depending on the individual and the situation in which is located;
- Variables were affecting the process of changing attitudes: on the one hand, the effect of the type of argument used and the experience of the recipient in the case of peripheral arguments; on the other hand, it refers to the intensity of cognitive thinking. Consequently, several variables can influence the process of changing attitudes in terms of intensity and use of the central, respectively, the peripheral way of arguing, as well as the intensity of the recipient's cognitive thinking;

- Variables were affecting message processing by recipients. The authors analyzed, on the one hand, the situational and personal variables affecting the recipient's motivation to process the report, on the other hand, they addressed variables that affect its ability to process the message. These variables influence the motivation to process the message relatively objectively in a way that increases or decreases the attention paid to the message arguments;
- How individuals process information. Variables that affect message processing to provide either positive or negative governance messages.
- Impact of motivation to process the message within the given processing method. If the recipient's motivation or ability to process the message's arguments decreases, then peripheral characters become relatively much more significant in the persuasion process and vice versa.
- Effects in terms of persistence of persuasion and uniqueness of central persuasion. Changing the recipient's attitude resulting from the processing of the information will be more durable over time, making consumer behavior much more accessible to estimate than changing the attitude achieved by using a peripheral persuasion.

The ELM model is a contribution to developing a marketing strategy for its ability to integrate relevant variables into governance to influence the recipient's attitude. The authors identified two elements determining the degree of motivation of the recipient to understand the message and its ability to do so. They also show two general cases of message processing to recipients in their own beliefs. In the first case, the arguments used in the article play an important and essential role. The recipient evaluates their quality, what the authors define as the perception of the individual because the arguments used are reliable. In the latter case, the effect of advertising design is more important than the influence of the arguments used. Thus, the recipient evaluates the marginal characters that can convince him. As an example, the use of sensitive music, scenes, trusted personality in advertising spots and the like.

3. Geographic Information Systems

The idea of geographic information systems can be dated to the late 1960s (Câmara et al. 2009). In the initial phase, geofomation systems were used mainly in areas necessary for general interests in the military, civil protection, forestry, mining industries, and only subsequently spread to other spheres. Nowadays, used in state administration and administration in the area of land management, in the commercial sphere in the planning of services, insurance, records of facilities (eg, engineering networks), logistics or in the area of the environment. By integrating geographic information systems into decision-making and planning processes, spatial variables have gained an essential role in the descriptive and explanatory variable (Tierno et al. 2013a). GIS technologies in telecommunications and navigation are gaining immense importance for individuals. GIS overcomes other information systems by allowing them to work simultaneously with spatial and non-spatial data, creating thematic maps rich in geographic information that couldn't be obtained from tabular or textual forms. The way of loading and collecting maps or other data in the form of layers enables complex analyzes to be performed by GIS (Cheng et al. 2005). The diagram of the multi-layer architecture of geographic information systems is shown in the figure (Fig. 2). Although each of the individual layers represents a separate unit, these units are interconnected and combinable through a coordination system and allow analysis created.

Figure 2. GIS multi-layer architecture (Krizan et al., 2015)

Geographic information systems offer these eight functions (Cheng et al. 2007):

- Using data from different sources: GIS can use and link location data from different sources and create databases that provide abundant application usage. The location is generally indicated by coordinates including geographic latitude, longitude, and altitude information. Geoformation systems can also link location information to spreadsheet information and convert them into a thematic map.
- Data retention: Geographic information systems are only capable of handling digital data. Therefore, some data needs to be digitized, which is sometimes a time-consuming process but can still be stored and used
- Data integration: Geographic information systems combine different map data to create and analyze different variables. If we have data on the number of inhabitants and their localization in the space, we can use GIS to get information about the most densely populated parts of the territory and thus the most significant number of potential customers. Data integration is possible through a geocoding process that overrides the implicit information (residency of the residents) with geographic information (the coordinates of the information).
- Display Technology: GIS technology allows to create traditional maps in which symbols represent physical objects or symbols — topographic maps, where the lines represent the shape and relief of the territory.
- Cartographic Projection Conversion: Before we can begin processing digital data, we must convert it into a standard cartographic projection, which is a primary cartographic and mathematical attribute. It includes transforming from a real three-dimensional world into a two-dimensional screen display or output on paper.
- Data Design: By allowing data used from different sources, GIS may be incompatible with each other. Through geoformation systems, we can convert standalone data to compatible data systems and work with them.
- Data Modeling: Generally, we know two types of models in GIS: vector and raster. While the former represents discrete elements depicting digital data in the form of dots, lines, or polygons, raster represents continuous numerical values and are more suitable for mapping land use maps.
- Data output: Output layers that produced in GIS can be subsequently displayed in digital form on screen or in print on paper. Based on these outputs, it is possible to pronounce conclusions and visualize or simulate possible solutions.

Geographic information systems have evolved considerably over their relatively short history. Perhaps the most significant change is the transformation of the GIS character. From the initially cartographically focused systems, they became critical analytical tools without which it would be time-consuming and in many cases impossible to process quantum data and draw conclusions from them. Geographic information systems have broadly expanded in number, size, functionality, and diversity. Despite the general boom that occurred in the implication of GIS in

everyday life, the growth of geographic information systems as essential tools in political decision-making is still considerably undersized in Slovakia. At the same time, they offer a wide range of tools used by different scientific circles, and we can also look for them in geomarketing.

4. GIS in Geomarketing

One of the essential elements of research in geography is a person whose identification in space is vital in many scientific disciplines. Therefore, its localization and analysis of its environment through GIS is increasingly needed. The integration of geographic information systems into the study of consumer behavior from a spatial, as well as a non-spatial perspective, opens the way for a new field of study called geomarketing (Baviera-Puig et al. 2009). It is clear from this that the consumer and the research tool - geographic information systems - are equally crucial for the emergence of geomarketing.

Geomarketing studies require a rich database of information and, together with cartographic information, we can use GIS to organize and process them. Databases can come from a variety of sources. Most often, however, data from internal sources of business companies (sales volume, company data, loyalty card data, etc.) or external institutions (various statistical data, census data, etc.). The map data comes from internal/external sources or directly modified by the user. GIS allows us to link databases with geographic information and perform a variety of analyzes that we go through a variety of tools. GIS tools play a key role in geomarketing research. Their application options range from the general tools used in many scientific spheres to niche tools and program extensions that designed explicitly for geomarketing research.

Geomarketing spatial data analysis can be performed through various applications and utilities. Although other applications are available on the market, the next section of the text focuses on GIS in ESRI's ArcGIS environment. The reason for this is the general popularity of this program and the number of geomarketing tools provided on the one hand and ESRI's most massive expansion in the GIS market on the other. One of the available ArcGIS utilities is Network Analyst. This extension allows users to perform spatial network analysis. The network can be understood as a system of interconnected points (nodes) of edges (lines). The network architecture so understood is documented in the figure (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Network edges and nodes (Li et al., 2003)

The great advantage of the ArcGIS Network Analyst extension is the ability to model real-world conditions, even dynamically. These conditions are, for example, traffic restrictions (maximum speed allowed, one-way roads), capacity options (tunnel height, bridge capacity), effective barriers (temporary closures), time rush time constraints or, in the case of public transport, breaks at stops. The hierarchical structure of the network, which classifies its parts (motorways, expressways, urban and interurban communications, etc.) along with the dynamic modeling of traffic restrictions, significantly improves networking and provides more realistic results of network analysis.

5. Conclusions

Research carried out the analyzed how emotion impact into ELM model on marketing activities. New consumer expectations are now being taken into account by business strategies that go beyond the strict vision of a rational individual, who is correctly informed and always makes a sensible choice to maximize the desired benefit. They also lead to new approaches to consumer behavior to address needs, motivation, and positive behavior.

The active and emotional component of consumer behavior emphasizes the importance of examining their impact on their decision to accept or reject an offer. While there are already several consumer emotion models in marketing theory, it can be stated that there are still difficulties to determine the exact causes of the decision made. Despite this obstacle, different models can be used, which can be the basis of business action plans. For this reason, developing modern marketing approaches based on stimulating emotions is needed. The consumer's senses contribute to creating an attractive product offering that, in order to convince him, must focus on emphasizing the individual's personality according to the principles of differentiation.

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